

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

The Xist imprinting system effectors BRWD1/3, PBRM1 and CDYL2 regulate common targets.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Results

I. Tumor suppression is a target of control by the Xist-associated imprinting effectors

The tumor suppressor APC was a central target of the imprinting effector genes.

Nf2 was also a shared BRWD/CDYL/PBRM genomic target

While p53 was not significantly co-regulated by the imprinting effectors, Rb1 was, but more modestly so than APC and Nf2.

Cyld was also a modest target of BRWD/PBRM/CDYL regulation.

These data supported a role for these effectors in transformation: as mediators of a tumor suppressor -induced cycling restriction signal, or themselves functioning directly as regulators of tumor suppression, activating APC in response to genomic instability resulting in Xist induction

II. Nuclear factors specific to imprinting: identification of epigenetic machinery and nuclear factors controlled by BRWD/PBRM/CDYL.

We identified a broad but specific network of epigenetic machinery that functioned downstream of BRWD1, PBRM and CDYL/CDYL2.

- Kdm5a
- Nr2c2
- Ncoa3
- Ncor1
- Jmjd1c
- Btaf1
- Tcf12
- Gtf2a1
- Nfat5
- Smarcd1
- Ash1l
- Bdp1
- Tet2 and Tet3
- Phf20 and Phf8
- Phc3
- Kat6a
- Mbd5
- Mll, Mll3 and Mll5

Ep300 was a shared imprinting effector regulatory target.

Discussion

The genes identified function as effectors of a gene regulation mechanism that balances homeostatic shifts by managing transcriptional noise through epigenetic regulation, a process involving the ncRNA Xist and associated machinery.